

EXPLORING TRANSPARENCY: POLICE OFFICERS' VIEW ON THE USE OF PNP BODY-WORN CAMERA

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to describe the perception of the police officers assigned in operations units of the PNP as regards the use of Body-Worn Camera and Alternative Recording Devices (ARDs) during the conduct of operations in compliance with the Rules on Body-Worn Camera issued by the Supreme Court in August 2021. The focus of the research is to determine how the police officers perceive the policy on the use of BWCs and ARDs particularly its necessity, practicability, effectiveness and the level of complexity of the preparation of the documents required by the court to be submitted in relation to its use. The result of show overall positive perceptions among police officers as regards the use of BWCs and ARDs. Comparative analysis of the data shows that police officers agree that BWC and ARD are necessary, practical and effective tool in the conduct of police operations. Likewise, police officers agree that the level of complexity of court required document to be submitted is reasonable. Nevertheless, amendments to the policy on the use of BWCs and ARDs are necessary to maximize the benefits of the said technology for the betterment of police operations.

Keywords: *PNP Body-Worn Camera, Police Operations, Extrajudicial Killings, Service of Warrants, Supreme Court Rules on Body-Worn Camera*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines, as a republican and democratic state, is duty-bound to ensure peace and order, protect life, liberty, and property and promote general welfare. It is in this light that the Constitution specifically mandates the State to maintain peace and order, administer justice, and to serve and protect the people.(1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 5, Article II, n.d.)

These primordial duties of the State are vital in the fulfilment of the purpose that the Constitution seeks to achieve as enunciated in the preamble --- *to build a just and humane society and establish a Government that shall embody our ideals and aspirations, promote the common good, conserve and develop our patrimony, and secure to ourselves and our posterity the blessings of independence and democracy under the rule of law and a regime of truth, justice, freedom, love, equality, and peace.*(1987 Constitution, Preamble, n.d.)

The maintenance of peace and order, proper administration of justice, protection of the people and promotion of general welfare necessarily carry with it the duty of the State to enforce the law. The law is vital because it serves as a guide as to what is accepted in a society, and without which, conflicts between and among citizens will arise. It shall be emphasized however that the law is useless if it will not be enforced. Thus, the enforcement of law is equally important as the existence of law.

To give life to law enforcement function of the State, the Constitution mandates the establishment and maintenance of *one police force, which shall be national in scope and civilian in character.*(1987 Constitution, Section 6, Article XVI, n.d.) In compliance to the said constitutional mandate, the Philippine National Police (PNP) was created under Republic Act 6975 otherwise known as the Department of the Interior and Local Government Act of 1990, and the PNP was subsequently placed under the control and supervision of the National Police Commission (NAPOLCOM) pursuant to Republic Act 8551 otherwise known as the Philippine National Police Reform and Reorganization Act of 1998.

Republic Act 6975 provides among others, that the PNP shall (1) enforce laws and ordinances relative to the protection of lives and properties, (2) maintain peace and order and take all necessary steps to ensure public safety, (3) investigate and prevent crimes, effect the arrest of criminal offenders, bring offenders to justice and assist in their prosecution, and (4) exercise general powers to make arrest, search and seizure in accordance with the Constitution and pertinent laws.(Republic Act 6975, Section 24, n.d.)

Primarily, the duty of the PNP is to enforce the law in order to maintain peace and order in the country. Concomitant to this duty is the obligation of the PNP to uphold the Constitution and obey legal orders of the duly-constituted authorities. The fulfilment of such solemn duty can only be carried out by safeguarding the constitutionally guaranteed rights of individual provided under the Bill of Rights. This Bill of Rights, particularly found in Article III of the 1987 Constitution, refers to the declaration and enumeration of

fundamental civil and political rights of a person which purpose is to protect him or her from the abuses committed by the government through its agent.(Villareal, 2017)

The Bill of Rights primarily mandates that *no person shall be deprived of life, liberty, or property without due process of law, nor shall any person be denied the equal protection of the laws.*(1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 1, Article III, n.d.)

The prohibition against the deprivation of life, liberty or property under the Bill of Rights is not absolute. In fact, a person may be deprived of his property, or liberty or even life, if found guilty beyond reasonable doubt of an offense or felony defined and penalized under the existing penal statutes. Nevertheless, this deprivation of liberty or life shall not take place unless due process was strictly observed, and that a speedy, impartial and public trial had been conducted.(1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 14, Article III, n.d.)

The Philippines, in compliance with the constitutional mandate to respect human rights and value the dignity of a person, is obliged to perform its duty to keep the community safe against lawless elements, and at the same time, regard full respect and observe the fundamental rights of all persons, including those arrested, suspected, and even convicted criminal offenders.

As eloquently explained by the Supreme Court of the Philippines, in the case of *People v. Sapla, citing the case of Tudtud*, to quote:

“... the Bill of Rights is the bedrock of constitutional government. If people are stripped naked of their rights as human beings, democracy cannot survive and government becomes meaningless. This explains why the Bill of Rights, contained as it is in the Article III of the Constitution, occupies a position of primacy in the fundamental law way above the articles on governmental powers.”(*People v. Sapla, G.R. No. 204045 (2020)*, n.d.)

The “freedom” and “equality” of the people, which the Bill of Rights seeks to protect, are sacrosanct concepts safeguarded by International Human Rights Law through the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. This Universal Declaration of Human Rights is document embodying the agreement of the countries on the freedoms and rights that deserve universal protection in order for every individual to live their lives freely, equally and in dignity.(Amnesty International, 2024)

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, among others, provides that everyone *is entitled in full equity to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.* (*Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 10*, n.d.)

As one of its obligations, the Philippines is bound to comply with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as it is a generally accepted principle of international law, following the mandates of the Constitution that *the Philippines adopts the generally accepted principles of international law as part of the law of the land and adheres to the*

policy of peace, equality, justice, freedom, cooperation, and amity with all nations.(1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 2, Article II, n.d.)

With these constitutional duties, the State is burdened with the obligation to strictly observe due process requirements before a person may be legally deprived of his or her life, liberty or property. In the legal parlance, there is a definite process to effect deprivation of life or liberty, termed as Criminal Procedure. It is the method prescribed by law for the apprehension and prosecution of persons accused of a criminal offense, and their punishment in case of conviction.(Pamaran, 2012)

The due process requirement is strictly observed in Criminal Procedure. It has been said that a day in court is the touchstone of the right to due process. *Procedural due process is that which hears before it condemns, which proceeds upon inquiry and renders judgment only after trial. It contemplates notice and opportunity to be heard before judgment is rendered affecting one's person or property.*(*Macabingkil v. Yatco, et.al., G.R. No. L-23147 (1967)*, n.d.)

Subsequent to the prosecution and punishment of a person found liable for commission of a crime or offense is the correction and rehabilitation as an integral part of the Criminal Justice System. Criminal Justice System is the network of the government and private agencies intended to manage accused and convicted criminals. (Crowder & Turvey, 2013)

In an article entitled *The Role and Function of the Prosecution in the Philippine Criminal Justice System*, Criminal Justice System is defined as the *system or process in the community by which crimes are investigated, and the persons suspected thereof are taken into custody, prosecuted in court and punished, if found guilty, provisions being made for their correction and rehabilitation.*(Valle-Corpuz, n.d.)

The correction and rehabilitation of offenders are in line with the concept of Restorative Justice, focusing on the reparation and restitution of offender and resolution of issues arising from a crime. In Restorative Justice, the remorseful offenders accept the responsibility of their misconduct and thus, creates an obligation to make things right, by undertaking solutions which promote repair, reconciliation and reassurance. The Philippines, a member-country of the Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, adopted the "Basic Principles on the Use of Restorative Justice Programmes in Criminal Matters". This is congruent with the goal of the Philippine Government to establish a humane correctional system that will promote the reformation of the offenders, and thus, will reduce the incidence of recidivism.(*Restorative Justice, Probation and Parole Administration*, n.d.)

The 1987 Constitution, United Nations Declaration on Human Rights, the Criminal Justice System and the Theory of Restorative Justice, among others, are legal instruments safeguarding individual's right to due process and prohibit human rights violations.

However, despite the existence of these legal instruments, deplorable acts of human rights violations committed by police force, military, and other security forces of the State have been an ordinary newscast. In an article entitled *Philippines: End Police Torture, Killings*, then President Aquino was urged to act decisively to punish the police and other state security forces who committed torture and extrajudicial killings. In the said article, it was emphasized that the progress in the justice system was overshadowed by failures to address other longstanding problems of human rights violations. (*Philippines: End Police Torture, Killings*, 2015)

Upon the assumption of office of the then President Rodrigo R. Duterte, the “War on Drugs” was implemented purposely to reduce the proliferation of dangerous drugs in the country. This campaign however was opposed by human rights groups claiming that this has led to the deaths of over 12,000 Filipinos, mostly urban poor. It was also alleged that at least 2,555 of the killings have been perpetrated by the PNP and worst, senior officials have instigated and incited the killings, which could amount to crime against humanity. (*Philippines’ “War on Drugs,”* n.d.)

The killings related to the “War on Drugs” have been labelled as “Extrajudicial Killings”. Extrajudicial killings, as defined by Black’s Law Dictionary, are those killings done outside the course of a regular judicial proceedings. (*Black’s Law Dictionary*, n.d.) As it is committed outside the bounds of the law, extrajudicial killing is considered as act of impunity and a violation of a person’s right to due process. According to the United Nations Human Rights Special Rapporteur, extrajudicial, summary, or arbitrary executions, which referred to the deliberate killing of individuals outside of any legal framework, are a violation of the most fundamental right. (*United Nations Human Rights Special Rapporteur*, n.d.)

In 2019, then Senator Leila De Lima re-filed a bill which sought to strengthen the Commission on Human Rights, the National Bureau of Investigation and the PNP in investigating extrajudicial killings. More importantly, the bill sought to ensure that police officers will have the highest regard for human rights and rule of law in performing their sworn duties. (PhilStar, 2019)

It is not entirely correct however to condemn police officers in every operations involving death of a suspect. It is to be noted that not all extrajudicial killing is unlawful and an act of human rights violations. The Revised Penal Code provides for justifying circumstances that will absolve the police officer from criminal and civil liability, i.e., *Self-Defense* and *Fulfilment of a Lawful Duty*.

In Self-Defense, any person who acted in defense of himself or herself, or of his property, or of his or her relative, or of stranger does not incur any criminal liability provided that the three requisites are present, such as: Unlawful aggression, Reasonable necessity of the means employed to repel the aggression, and Lack of sufficient provocation on the part of the person defending himself or herself. (Revised Penal Code, Article 11 Paragraphs 1 to 3, n.d.) In Fulfilment of Lawful on the other hand, a public

officer acting in lawful exercise of duty or right of office is justified in case of injury or death that resulted therefrom.(Revised Penal Code, Article 11, Paragraph 5, n.d.)

The PNP Police Operational Procedure set forth guidelines on the use of force and firearms during police operations, in which, use of necessary force is allowed whenever necessary in enforcing law and maintaining peace and order, and also, use of firearms is allowed if the offender possess imminent danger of causing death or injury to the police officer or other persons.(*PNP Police Operational Procedures, RULES 7 and 8*, n.d.)

Most killings resulting from police operations, particularly during the height of the “War on Drugs”, as claimed by police operatives, are result of either Self-Defense or Fulfillment of Duty. These narratives however, are widely disputed by Human Rights Groups, and resulted to the landmark step of the International Criminal Court --- the conduct of investigation in the killings relative to this government anti-illegal drug efforts.(McCarthy, 2021)

The predicament however, is that, in these police operations, more often than not, there were no disinterested eye-witness available to attest to the veracity of the claim of police officers of self-defense and lawful performance of duty. In 2017, a 26-year-old alleged drug suspect was arrested by police officers and thereafter killed in a claim of self-defense on the part of the police officers.(Gavilan, 2023)

In 2018, three police officers were convicted for the crime of Murder in relations to the death of a 17-year-old minor, during a drug sweep operation. The police officers claimed that the minor, who was a drug runner, drew a gun and fired at them, and hence, they returned fire in self-defense. To bolster their version of the incident, police officers showed official photograph of the crime scene with a gun and packets of methamphetamine next to victim’s body. But the CCTV footage shows otherwise. The truth, as shown in the footage is, the three police officers dragged the minor into an alley, minutes before he was found dead. (Sullivan, 2018)

In an article published in Human Rights Watch, the narrations of police officers conducting drug raids are unreliable because these officers have been shown to manufacture evidence such as, planting of weapon and drugs, to justify the killing. (Conde, 2019)

In 2018, the PNP issued Memorandum Circular (MC) 2018-009, with subject *Operational Guidelines and Policies on the Use of Body Worn Camera*. This accordingly, is in recognition of the essential role of the trust and mutual respect of the law enforcement agencies and the community towards effective policing.

The Concept of Operation under PNP MC 2018-009 is consist of three phases, such as, the Pre-Operation Phase, Operations Phase, and Post Operations Phase.

The Pre-Operations Phase provides for the establishment of Command Center to properly record, monitor, oversee, evaluate and audit the actual police operations. It is

likewise provided that the trainings shall be conducted for the designated uniformed personnel and units on the proper care, maintenance and operations, and use of Body-Worn Camera (BWC). The Operation Phase provides among others, that the BWC shall be used in all planned operations and other law enforcement activities whenever possible and applicable. The Post Operations Phase on the other hand, provides that BWC shall be turned over to the team leader for submission to IT/BWC Custodian after operations for the downloading and storage of the data. (*PNP Memorandum Circular 2018-009*, n.d.)

Notwithstanding the fact that PNP MC 2018-009 provides administrative sanctions for its violation, in 2019 however, then PNP Chief Guillermo Eleazar said that police officers could not be forced to wear BWC. Accordingly, although Eleazar agrees that BWC could not be of help in promoting transparency amid questionable death linked to the war on drugs, still he claimed, that there is no law that requires the police officers to wear bodycams. (Balagtas-See, 2021)

Shortly after this claim, the Supreme Court issued Rules on the Use of Body Worn Camera in the Execution of Warrants. This issuance of the Supreme Court in effect amended the Rules on Criminal Procedure. Under this Rule, the police officers serving Warrant of Arrest and implementing Search Warrant, shall have one BWC and one Alternative Recording Device (ARD). In case of unavailability of BWC, there shall be a minimum of two ARDs. In cases of Warrantless Arrest, the use of BWC and ARDs shall be complied with insofar as it is practicable. (*A.M. No. 21-06-08-SC*, n.d.)

Pursuant to the Rules on BWC issued by the Supreme Court, failure to observe the rules during the implementation of Search Warrant shall render the evidence confiscated inadmissible, and the officers concerned shall be liable for contempt of court. On the other hand, the rule is different in service of Warrant of Arrest, or during Warrantless Arrest. Accordingly, failure to use BWC and ARDs during the service of Warrant of Arrest or during Warrantless Arrest shall not render the evidence confiscated inadmissible, provided that the non-compliance thereof can be justified by the operating officers. Nevertheless, deliberate failure of police officers to use BWC and ARD during service of Warrant of Arrest or conduct of Warrantless Arrest shall render the officer liable for contempt of court.

The Supreme Court further requires that the video recording from BWC and ARD shall be accompanied by an affidavit detailing the circumstances of the arrest or implementation of Search Warrant. It also provides for the Chain of Custody of the recordings as a measure to avoid improper access, review and tampering.

In an article published in *Inquirer.Net*, it was mentioned that the Supreme Court issued the Rules on Body-Worn Camera during implementation of Search Warrant and service of Warrant of Arrest in response to the calls from lawyers, human rights groups, and advocates due to the increasing incidents of extrajudicial killings. (Torres-Tupas, 2021)

According to Braga, et.al., (2018), police officers equipped with BWCs have fewer complaints and use of force reports than those officers without BWC. It was further found that officers with BWC made more arrests and issued more citations than those who were not equipped with BWC. The findings suggests that the use of BWCs resulted in the de-escalation of aggression, or have created a civilizing effect on the nature of police-citizen encounters. It is thus concluded that the reduction of complaints and use of force attributed to the use of BWCs is important in improving police-community relations.(Braga et al., 2018)

In 2021, Williams, et.al., claimed that BWCs can reduce police use of force incidents by 10% and civilian complaints against law enforcers by 15%. Based on the findings, BWC provides a considerable return on public investment and the benefits of its use outweighs its cost.(Williams, et al., 2021)

In an article entitled *Benefits and Barriers to Implementing Police Body-Worn Cameras*, the use of BWC was adopted by several police department across Canada and the United States purposely to utilize this new technology in an attempt to increase police transparency with certainty due to limited academic literature and pilot projects showing mixed results in its effectiveness in reducing excessing use of force by law enforcement officers. Accordingly, the use of force of police officers in line of duty is actually, an institution sub-culture. This institutional sub-culture is the collective mindset shaped by organizational procedures, incentives, management, and behaviors that plays a crucial role that explains the similar reaction of law enforcement officers to particular situations. Evidence suggests that the use of BWC can standardize the officer's reaction in various situations and this will lead to increased accountability that will continue even they are not equipped with BWCs, due to the increased levels of self-awareness and self-scrutiny brought about by the continuous use of BWC.(*Benefits and Barriers to Implementing Police Body-Worn Cameras*, n.d.)

On the contrary, Lee (2021) stated that BWC have little to no impact on policing, whether in preventing police violence or holding police accountable after the fact. Lee argued that the footage from BWC is being recorded from the officer's point of view, and worst, controlled by law enforcement. The footage taken from the BWC can be incomplete, and may be manipulated to bolster the narratives of the law enforcement officers.(Lee, 2021)

In the Philippines, the mandatory use of BWC by the PNP was sensationalized due to incident involving police officers assigned with Navotas Police Station who killed a 17-year-old boy, but the said police operation was not recorded in BWCs. The Chief of Police reasoned out that the police officers left their BWCs turned off during the operations as the devices run out of batteries. Due to this incident, Senator Sherwin Gatchalian filed Senate Bill 1057 or the proposed Police On-Body Cam Act which will require all law enforcers to use on-body cameras and shall leave the same turned on and running until the termination of the operations. It was explained that the function of the on-body camera will be two-pronged: protect the public against police misconduct by improving law enforcement accountability and help protect our police men from false and uncorroborated accusations of abuse.(Chi, 2023)

In examining the perception of the police officers, the effectiveness of the use of BWC and ARDs during police operations to suppress extrajudicial killings and human rights violations committed by police officers will be assessed and evaluated to serve as basis to test the existing policy or develop a new one.

Research Questions

This study intends to describe the perception of the police officers in the use of BWC and ARDs as basis for recommendation or solution to address emerging issues in the conduct of police operations. Specifically, this aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents based on:
 - a. Rank;
 - b. Designation; and
 - c. No. of years in the PNP service?

2. How do police officers perceive the use of BWC and ARDs in terms of the following:
 - a. Necessity of the use of BWC and ARDs during police operations;
 - b. Practicability of the use of BWC during police operations;
 - c. Effectiveness of the use of BWC to prove proper conduct of police operations; and
 - d. Level of complexity of documents to be submitted in Court in relation to BWC requirement?

3. From the point-of-view of the police officers, what measures or policy can be implemented in relation to the use of BWC and ARDs in terms of:
 - a. Necessity;
 - b. Practicality;
 - c. Effectiveness; and
 - d. Complexity of court required documents.

METHODOLOGY

The primary goal of this study is to determine the perception of the police officers in the use of BWC and ARDs as basis for recommendation or solution to address emerging issues in the conduct of police operations.

To achieve said objective, this study has adopted the Mixed-Method Triangulation Design. The Triangulation Design is the most common and well-known approach to mixing methods.(Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018) This design is utilized to obtain different but complementary data on the same topic in order to understand the research problem. By applying this design, the differing strengths and nonoverlapping weaknesses of quantitative methods and of qualitative methods are brought together.(Patton, 1990) This design was used considering that the study intends to directly compare and contrast

quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings, and to validate or expand quantitative results with qualitative data.

In particular, this study adopted the Concurrent Triangulation Research Design. The Concurrent Triangulation involves a single study containing qualitative and quantitative data collection which is conducted at the same time. The purpose of this type of investigation is to validate the findings generated by each method through evidence produced by the other. (Kroll & Neri, 2009)

The researchers based this study on the critical analysis of pertinent laws, rules and regulations, supplemented by survey and interview.

As to the Survey Questionnaire, the first part of which indicates respondents name, which the respondent has the option not to answer, designation, and the years of service in the PNP. The second part of the questionnaire is a checklist composed of 20 items, in which the respondents were asked to answer each question by encircling their responses using the scale: *1 – Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Undecided, 4 – Agree and 5 – Strongly Agree*. The results of the survey provide an approximation of the general perception as the respondents may have over or under assessed their answers.

The first part of the survey questionnaire is consistent with the details in the Personal Data Sheet (PDS) of the respondents. The researchers did not include the parts of the PDS that are not needed in this study.

The Content Validity Index is utilized to assess the suitability and clarity of various statements related to the necessity, practicality, effectiveness, and complexity of Court-required documents in utilizing BWC and ARD during police operations. Each aspect has a set of statements evaluated validators, who are content experts, indicating their agreement with the relevance of the statement.

The computed I-CVI (Item Content Validity Index) for all statements is 1, indicating full agreement among validators regarding the relevance of each statement. Similarly, the Scale Content Validity Index (S-CVI) and SCVI/UA (Universal Agreement) are also 1, indicating unanimous agreement among validators regarding the relevance of all statements in this aspect. This suggests a high level of agreement among validators that the use of BWC and ARD is essential for various police operations. Moreover, all tables who an Item-Level Face Validity Index (I-FVI) of 1, indicating complete agreement among validators regarding the clarity of each statement. The Scale-Level Face Validity Index/Average (S-FVI/Ave) is also 1, showing universal agreement across all statement. This suggests strong consensus among validators that the statements are clear and directly applicable to the context of the study.

The unanimous agreement among validators on both the content validity and face validity indices indicates a high level of consensus regarding the relevance and clarity of the statements, affirming the essential role of BWC and ARD in police operations, thus, necessitating the piloting of the study.

The reliability coefficients, as indicated by Cronbach alpha, offer valuable insights into the consistency and dependability of the measurement scales used in the assessment. In the domain **NECESSITY**, the coefficient stands impressively high at $\alpha = 0.910$, reflecting an excellent level of internal consistency among the items assessing this aspect. This suggests that the items within this category consistently measure the intended construct with a high degree of reliability.

In contrast, the aspect of **PRACTICALITY** initially presents a somewhat lower coefficient of $\alpha = 0.687$, indicating a level of reliability that could be improved. However, through the removal of certain items, notably item 4, the coefficient could be raised to $\alpha = 0.759$, rendering it acceptable. Further refinement by eliminating items 5 and 6 could potentially elevate the reliability to 0.803, categorizing it as good, but it is not recommended.

In terms of **EFFECTIVENESS**, the coefficient is notably high at $\alpha = 0.918$, indicating excellent internal consistency. Although there is a possibility of a slight improvement to 0.923 by removing item 3, this adjustment might not be necessary given the already excellent reliability.

Finally, the aspect of **COMPLEXITY OF COURT-REQUIRED DOCUMENTS**, demonstrates an outstanding level of reliability with a Cronbach alpha of $\alpha = 0.930$, confirming the high internal consistency of the items within this domain.

Overall, these reliability coefficients provide valuable guidance for the refinement and interpretation of the assessment measure, enabling researchers to make informed decisions regarding their validity and reliability.

Likewise, a Structured Interview was conducted. The researchers prepared questions regarding respondents' view on how they perceive the use of BWC and ARDs during police operations, in terms of *necessity, practicability, effectiveness and the complexity of the Court-required documents*, and what measures or policy can be implemented to optimize the utilization of this technology for the betterment of the organization and for the benefit of the public.

The study covered 100 police officers-respondents, out of 225 police operatives from Mandaluyong City Police Station. However, during the retrieval of the Survey Questionnaire, only 90 responses were collated by the researchers. The respondents in this research were police officers in Sub-Stations (Sub-Station 1 to 9) of Mandaluyong City Police Station. The researcher used Purposive Sampling Technique. Purposive sampling involves an iterative process of selecting research subject rather than starting with a predetermined sampling frame.(Robinson, 2014)

The researchers conducted documentary analysis on the facts and information gathered from laws, rules and regulations, journals, studies, and researchers both from foreign and local origin pertaining to peace and order, human rights violations during

police operations and use of BWCs to deter police abuses and improve human rights-based policing.

The data gathered from the survey questionnaire for this study were collated, tabulated, analysed and interpreted in several tables using statistical methods, i.e., *frequency and percentage distribution, mean and standard deviation*.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What is the profile of the respondents?

1.1. Rank

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents according to rank. The largest group comprises Police Corporals (40.00%), followed by Patrolmen/Patrolwomen (37.78%), and Police Staff Sergeants (22.22%).

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents according to Rank

Rank	Frequency	Percent (%)
Patrolman / Patrolwoman	34	37.78
Police Corporal	36	40.00
Police Staff Sergeant	20	22.22
Total	90	100.00

1.2 Designation

Table 2 illustrates the distribution of respondents according to their designations. The majority of respondents are Patrollers (74.44%), followed by Shift Supervisors (10.00%), Desk Officers (8.89%), and Mobile Crew members (6.67%).

Table 2

Distribution of Respondents according to Designation

Designation	Frequency	Percent (%)
Desk Officer	8	8.89
Mobile Crew	6	6.67
Patroller	67	74.44
Shift Supervisor	9	10.00
Total	90	100.00

1.3. Number of years in the PNP service

Table 3 provides the distribution of respondents according to their years of service. Many respondents have 6 to 10 years of service (62.22%), while the remaining have up to 5 years of service (37.78%).

Table 3

Distribution of Respondents according to Years in Service

Years	Frequency	Percent (%)
5 years	34	37.78
6 to 10 years	56	62.22
Total	90	100.00

Research Question 2. How do police officers perceive the use of BWC and ARDs in terms of the following:

2.1. Necessity of the use of BWC and ARDs during police operations

The result in Table 4 provides valuable insights into the perceived necessity of body-worn cameras (BWC) and alternative recording devices (ARD) in various policing activities.

Table 4

Police Officers' Views on the Necessity of PNP Body-Worn Cameras (BWCs) and Alternative Recording Devices (ARDs)

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Service of Warrant of Arrest cannot be done properly without the use of BWC and ARD.	3.46	1.17	Agree
2. Warrantless Arrest cannot be done properly without the use of BWC and ARD.	2.91	1.25	Undecided
3. Implementation of Search Warrant cannot be done properly without the use of BWC and ARD.	3.51	1.16	Agree
4. Police operatives shall be equipped with BWC to ensure proper performance of duty.	3.83	0.94	Agree
5. The legitimacy operation can only be proven by the recordings in BWC and ARD.	3.73	1.04	Agree
Overall	3.49	0.32	Agree

2.2. Practicability of the use of BWC and ARDs during police operations

The data in Table 5 reveals a general agreement on the practicability of these technologies, albeit with some nuances in certain areas.

Table 5

Police Officers' Views on the Practicability of PNP Body-Worn Cameras (BWCs) and Alternative Recording Devices (ARDs)

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. The rules on the use of BWC and ARD to be observed by police operatives are reasonable.	3.92	0.86	Agree
2. Police operatives strictly observe the rules without experiencing any challenge in logistics, and human resource.	3.50	1.02	Agree
3. The use of BWC and ARD aids the police operatives in the conduct of police operations.	3.77	1.04	Agree
4. There is sufficient number of BWC and ARD in the police stations/ units to be used by police officers in the conduct of police operations.	3.23	1.18	Undecided
5. Police operatives are trained to use and maintain PNP issued BWC and ARD.	3.62	0.97	Agree
6. Utilization and maintenance of BWC and ARD is cost-efficient.	3.71	0.93	Agree
Overall	3.63	0.22	Agree

2.3. Effectiveness of the use of BWC to prove proper conduct of police operations

The findings in Table 6 indicate a strong consensus on the positive impact of these technologies on various aspects of policing.

Table 6

Police Officers' Views on the Effectiveness of PNP Body-Worn Cameras (BWCs) and Alternative Recording Devices (ARDs)

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. The use of BWC and ARD enhances the transparency and accountability of police officers.	4.04	0.72	Agree
2. The use of BWC and ARD provides an unbiased records of police encounters.	4.03	0.87	Agree
3. The use of BWC and ARD increased the performance of police officers in the conduct of police operations to suppress criminal activities.	3.88	0.93	Agree
4. The use of BWC and ARD aids the prosecution to secure conviction of arrested suspects during police operations.	4.02	0.81	Agree
5. The use of BWC and ARD aids the police officers in defending themselves in service-connected cases filed against them.	4.11	0.74	Agree
Overall	4.02	0.08	Agree

2.4. Level of complexity of documents to be submitted in Court in relation to BWC requirement.

The findings in Table 7 indicate a strong consensus among officers on their ability to manage these requirements effectively.

Table 7

Police Officers' Views on the Complexity of Court-Required Documents Related to the Use of PNP Body-Worn Cameras (BWCs) and Alternative Recording Devices (ARDs)

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Police operatives who utilized BWC and ARD are well-trained in preparation of documents/ affidavits to be submitted in court as required under the rules on BWC.	3.89	0.92	Agree
2. Police operatives who conducted police operations with BWC and ARD are able to submit in Court the required documents.	3.84	0.92	Agree
3. The documents/Affidavits to be submitted in Court is reasonable and can be complied with within the required period.	3.79	0.80	Agree
4. Police operatives strictly comply with the required Court compliance in relation to the use of BWC and ARD without experiencing any difficulty.	3.69	0.96	Agree
Overall	3.80	0.07	Agree

In sum, the result in Table 8 below presents a comparative analysis of body-worn cameras (BWC) and alternative recording devices (ARDs) based on four dimensions: **Necessity, Practicability, Effectiveness, and Complexity of Court-Required Documents**. The results show overall positive perceptions among police officers, as indicated by the mean scores in each category.

Table 8

Use of BWC and ARDs: Comparative Analysis

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Necessity	3.49	0.32	Agree
Practicability	3.63	0.22	Agree
Effectiveness	4.02	0.08	Agree
Complexity of Court Required Documents	3.80	0.07	Agree

Overall	3.74	0.20	Agree
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Research Question 3. From the point-of-view of police officers, what measures or policy can be implemented in relation to the use of BWCs and ARDs in terms of:

6.4. Necessity

During the conduct of the interview, it was also pointed out that the BWCs and ARDs must be part of the uniform, hence, all police personnel must have an officially-issued BWC or ARD as the case may be. It is also necessary that the BWC and ARD are full-capable and technologically advanced in order to benefit from its full potential. Further, it was suggested that the training on the use and proper handling of BWC and ARD must be incorporated in the Basic Recruit Course of the PNP to enable the newly graduate police officers shall be equipped the moment that they will be deployed to their respective duties. Moreover, police officers-respondents pointed out that there shall be a system for storage and management of recorded data in order to maintain the integrity of the recordings and protect the privacy rights of the individuals arrested or subject of the police operations.

6.4. Practicability

In terms of practicability, the police officers-respondents emphasized that the BWC and the ARDs must be obligatory, only if BWC and ARD are available or issued to the police operatives. Also, police officers-respondents are of the view that the use of BWC and ARD shall only be used in overt police operations, and shall not be required in covert police activities. It was also highlighted that the police operatives shall have advanced and continuous training on the use and maintenance of BWC and ARD.

6.4. Effectiveness

As to the effectiveness, according to the police officers-respondents, the BWC and ARD to be procured shall be capable of recording comprehensive footage of events, i.e., clear video and audio recording, and long battery life. Also, there shall be a system to be implemented in order to monitor the compliance of the police operatives during operations. Likewise, some police officers-respondents suggested that the PNP shall raise awareness among citizens about the use and purpose of BWC and ARD.

6.4. Complexity of Court-Required Documents

With regard to the complexity of documents required in court, police officers-respondents are of the view that extensive training and seminars on the preparation of Affidavits of Arrest, Affidavits of Police Operatives, among others, shall be continuously conducted to all police operatives in order for them to efficiently comply with the requirements of the court.

DISCUSSION

The Profile of the Respondents

As to the profile of the respondents in terms of rank, Table 1 shows that the largest group comprises Police Corporals (40.00%), followed by Patrolmen/Patrolwomen (37.78%), and Police Staff Sergeants (22.22%). This distribution indicates a significant representation of lower and mid-level ranks, which can influence the overall perspective on BWCs and ARDs. Lower-ranking officers, such as Patrolmen/Patrolwomen, Police Corporal and Police Staff Sergeant, are typically more involved in direct, on-the-ground operation, where the practical benefits and challenges of BWCs and ARDs are most apparent. Their higher frequency suggests that the data reflects the experiences and views of those most frequently engaging with the public and potentially using BWC and ARD extensively.

As to the designation, Table 2 illustrates the distribution of respondents according to the particular police work they perform. The majority of the respondents are patrollers (74.44%), followed by Shift Supervisors (10.00%), Desk Officers (8.89%), and Mobile Crew members (6.67%). The predominance of patrollers, who are primarily responsible for field duties, highlights a focus on active policing roles. This group's significant representation suggests that the insights provided are deeply rooted in practical, operational experiences with BWCs and ARDs. Given their primary role in law enforcement activities, patrollers are likely to offer valuable feedback on the effectiveness and practicability of these technologies.

As to the number of years in the service, Table 3 above shows the distribution of respondents according to the years of their service with the PNP. Majority of the respondents have 6 to 10 years of service (62.22%), while the remaining were in the service for 5 years and below (37.78%). The distribution indicates a blend of relatively experienced officers alongside those who are newer to the police force. Officers with 6 to 10 years of experience likely have a well-rounded view of the traditional policing methods and the integration of new technologies like BWCs and ARDs. Their insights can provide a balanced perspective on how these devices impact policing practices over time, including adjustments in procedures and attitudes toward transparency and accountability.

Respondents' perspective on the use of BWC and ARDS as to its necessity during police operations

Table 4 above provides insights on the perceptions of the police officers-respondents on the necessity of BWCs and ARDs in various policing activities and operations. The data indicate that respondents agree on the importance of these technologies, although opinions vary depending on the context of their use.

In context of serving warrants of arrest, officers agree ($M = 3.46$, $SD = 1.17$) that BWCs and ARDs are essential. This agreement highlights the belief that these devices

enhance the accuracy and integrity of such operations, potentially reducing disputes about the conduct of arrests. Similarly, there is a strong consensus ($M = 3.51$, $SD = 1.16$) regarding the necessity of BWCs and ARDs during the implementation of search warrants, suggesting that officers recognize the value of recorded evidence in ensuring procedural compliance and protecting against misconduct allegations.

However, when it comes to warrantless arrests, the response is more ambivalent ($M = 2.91$, $SD = 1.25$). This undecided stance may stem from the spontaneous nature of such situations, where the practical challenges of using BWCs effectively come into play. Officers might be uncertain about the feasibility and immediate benefits of activating BWCs in high-pressure, unpredictable scenarios.

Despite this uncertainty, there is a strong agreement ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 0.94$) that police operatives should be equipped with BWCs to ensure proper performance of duty. This finding reflects a broad recognition among officers that BWCs can enhance their professionalism and accountability, likely leading to improved public trust. Furthermore, the belief that the legitimacy of operations can only be proven by recordings from BWCs and ARDs ($M = 3.73$, $SD = 1.04$) underscores the importance of these devices in documenting and verifying police actions, which can protect officers from false accusations and enhance the credibility of their operations.

The overall mean score of 3.49 ($SD = 0.32$) indicates a general agreement on the necessity of BWCs and ARDs across different operational contexts. The relatively low standard deviation suggests a consistent belief among officers regarding the value of these technologies. This consensus aligns with existing literature, which shows that BWCs increase accountability by providing objective records of police encounters (Ariel et al., 2015). Officers may feel that BWCs protect them from unfounded complaints and legal issues by capturing comprehensive evidence.

The presence of BWCs can lead to behavioral changes among both police officers and civilians, often resulting in more professional conduct (Ariel et al., 2016). This might explain why officers believe BWCs are crucial for ensuring proper performance of duty. Additionally, research has shown that BWCs are associated with reductions in complaints against officers and use-of-force incidents (Jennings et al., 2015). This could be why officers see BWCs as necessary for proving the legitimacy of their operations and ensuring proper conduct during arrests and searches.

BWCs and ARDs also provide clear and unbiased accounts of police activities, which are invaluable in legal contexts (Lum et al., 2015). Officers' agreement on the necessity of BWCs for serving warrants and conducting searches likely stems from the desire to have indisputable evidence in court. However, the undecided response regarding warrantless arrests may reflect practical challenges, such as the spontaneity of such situations in which activating a BWC may not always be feasible (Harris, 2010). Concerns about privacy and the management of BWC and ARD data might also contribute to this uncertainty.

Respondents' perspective on the use of BWC and ARDS as to its practicability

Table 5 above reveals a general agreement on the practicability of these technologies, albeit with some nuances in certain areas. Officers agree that the rules governing the use of BWCs and ARDs are reasonable ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.86$). This high level of agreement suggests that the regulations are perceived as fair and achievable within the scope of their duties. The reasonable nature of these rules likely contributes to their effective implementation, as officers are more likely to adhere to guidelines they view as logical and manageable.

Similarly, there is a consensus that police operatives strictly observe the rules without experiencing significant logistical or human resource challenges ($M = 3.50$, $SD = 1.02$). This indicates that, for the most part, officers find it feasible to comply with the established protocols. The relatively higher standard deviation here, however, suggests that while many officers agree, there is some variability in experiences, possibly due to differences in resource availability or operational contexts.

The use of BWCs and ARDs is also seen as beneficial in aiding police operations ($M = 3.77$, $SD = 1.04$). This agreement underscores the practical utility of these devices in everyday policing activities, enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of law enforcement efforts. The data suggests that officers recognize the value added by BWCs in terms of operational support and evidentiary benefits.

However, there is some ambivalence regarding the sufficiency of BWCs and ARDs available in police stations ($M = 3.23$, $SD = 1.18$). This undecided stance may reflect varying levels of equipment distribution across different units, with some officers experiencing shortages while others have adequate supplies. The higher SD here points to significant disparities in equipment availability, which could impact the consistent use of these technologies across the board.

Training on the use and maintenance of BWCs and ARDs is positively viewed, with officers agreeing that they are adequately trained ($M = 3.62$, $SD = 0.97$). Proper training is crucial for the effective deployment and maintenance of technology, and this agreement suggests that the PNP has invested in preparing its personnel to utilize these tools effectively. Furthermore, officers agree that the utilization and maintenance of BWCs and ARDs are cost-efficient ($M = 3.71$, $SD = 0.93$). This perception of cost efficiency is important for the sustainability of the BWC program, as it suggests that the benefits of using these devices outweigh the costs involved in their deployment and upkeep.

Overall, the mean score of 3.63 ($SD = 0.22$) indicates a general agreement on the practicability of BWCs and ARDs in police work. The low standard deviation suggests a consistent belief among officers regarding the practical benefits of these technologies.

The findings align with existing literature, which emphasizes the importance of clear and reasonable guidelines for the successful implementation of BWCs (Beller, 2021). Studies also highlight the need for adequate training to ensure that officers can

effectively use and maintain BWCs, which is reflected in the officers' agreement on training adequacy (White, 2014). The ambivalence about the sufficiency of BWCs and ARDs aligns with findings that resource distribution can be uneven, affecting the uniformity of technology implementation (Cubitt et al., 2017).

Respondents' perspective on the use of BWC and ARDS as to its effectiveness

Table 6 indicate a strong consensus on the positive impact of these technologies on various aspects of policing. Police officers overwhelmingly agree that the use of BWCs and ARDs enhances transparency and accountability ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.72$). This high level of agreement underscores the belief that recording devices provide a clear and objective account of police activities, which can increase public trust and ensure that officers adhere to professional standards. This finding is supported by existing literature, which highlights that BWCs can lead to significant improvements in police accountability (Ariel, Farrar, & Sutherland, 2015).

The perception that BWCs and ARDs provide unbiased records of police encounters is also strongly supported ($M = 4.03$, $SD = 0.87$). Officers recognize that these devices offer an impartial perspective that can be critical in evaluating the conduct of both police and civilians. This aligns with research suggesting that BWCs can serve as a neutral third party, offering credible evidence in disputes and investigations (Lum, Koper, & Merola, 2015).

Furthermore, officers agree that BWCs and ARDs have increased their performance in suppressing criminal activities ($M = 3.88$, $SD = 0.93$). The belief that these technologies improve operational efficiency and effectiveness is consistent with findings that suggest BWCs can enhance officer performance by encouraging adherence to procedures and reducing the likelihood of misconduct (A. Braga et al., 2017). The data also shows strong agreement that BWCs and ARDs aid in securing convictions during prosecutions ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.81$). This indicates that officers believe these recordings provide robust evidence that can substantiate their actions and support the prosecution's case. Literature supports this view, highlighting that video evidence from BWCs can be crucial in court, offering clear and compelling proof of events (White, 2014).

Additionally, officers agree that BWCs and ARDs help them defend themselves in service-connected cases ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.74$). This finding suggests that officers see these technologies as protective tools that can exonerate them from false accusations and demonstrate the legality of their actions. Research corroborates this perception, showing that BWCs can provide crucial exculpatory evidence that protects officers from unwarranted claims (Harris, 2010).

Overall, the mean score of 4.02 with a standard deviation of 0.08 indicates a strong and consistent agreement on the effectiveness of BWCs and ARDs. This low SD suggests a unified belief among officers regarding the benefits of these technologies in enhancing transparency, accountability, performance, and legal defense.

The findings align with existing literature, which emphasizes the multiple benefits of BWCs, including improved transparency, accountability, performance, and legal protection for officers (*Ariel et al., 2015; Lum et al., 2015; Jennings et al., 2015*). The high agreement on the effectiveness of BWCs in various aspects of policing indicates that these technologies are viewed as valuable tools that significantly contribute to the integrity and efficiency of police operations.

Respondents' perspective on the use of BWC and ARDS as to the level of complexity of documents required by the court

The results in Table 7 indicate a strong consensus among officers on their ability to manage these requirements effectively. Police officers agree that those who utilize BWCs and ARDs are well-trained in the preparation of documents and affidavits required by the court ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.92$). This agreement suggests that the training provided to officers is thorough and equips them with the necessary skills to handle legal documentation effectively. Such training is crucial because it ensures that the evidence captured by BWCs is presented in a manner that is acceptable in court, thereby enhancing the judicial process.

Additionally, officers agree that they are able to submit the required documents to the court following operations involving BWCs and ARDs ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.92$). This consistency indicates that the procedural requirements for submitting evidence are generally manageable and within the officers' capabilities. It reflects the officers' confidence in their ability to comply with legal standards, which is essential for the successful prosecution of cases.

The reasonableness of the document submission requirements is also acknowledged, with officers agreeing that these can be complied with within the required period ($M = 3.79$, $SD = 0.80$). This suggests that the deadlines and expectations set by the court are perceived as fair and achievable, allowing officers to fulfill their duties without undue pressure. The relatively lower SD here implies a consistent perception across different officers, indicating a broadly shared view of the reasonableness of these requirements.

Furthermore, officers agree that they strictly comply with court requirements related to the use of BWCs and ARDs without experiencing significant difficulty ($M = 3.69$, $SD = 0.96$). These findings highlight that, while there might be occasional challenges, the overall process of compliance is seen as manageable. The slight increase in standard deviation suggests some variability in experiences, which could be due to differences in individual cases or the complexity of specific operations.

Overall, the mean score of 3.80 ($SD = 0.07$) indicates a general agreement on the officers' ability to handle the complexity of court-required documents when using BWCs and ARDs. The low standard deviation reflects a consistent belief among officers that the training and procedural requirements are adequate and manageable.

The findings align with existing literature, which emphasizes the importance of comprehensive training and clear procedural guidelines in the effective use of BWCs in legal contexts (International Association of Chiefs of Police, 2019). Proper training ensures that officers are not only capable of using the technology but also proficient in preparing and submitting the necessary legal documentation. This enhances the overall effectiveness of BWCs in supporting law enforcement and judicial processes (*White, 2014*).

The measures or policies to be Implemented In relation to the use of BWCs and ARDs In terms of necessity, practicability, effectiveness and as to the complexity of the court required documents

As to the necessity, the officers pointed out that the use of BWC and ARD shall be imposed and the same shall be part of the uniform of the PNP. With this, a fully-capable and technologically advanced devices shall be procured by the PNP to obtain its optimum potential. Considering that the use of BWC and ARD is necessary, officers are of the view that it shall be included in the training for Basic Recruit Course of the PNP so as to equip the newly recruited police officers. The officers further find it necessary that a system for storage and management of recorded data shall be developed in order to maintain the integrity of the recordings and uphold the right of the citizens subject of the arrest or police operations to privacy.

The view of the officers is rational since making the BWC and ARD part of the PNP uniform shall compel the police officers to carry the said devices for the entire duration of their duties. Also, the BWC and ARD shall be capable and advanced so as to use its full potential, such, it can provide audio recording, clear video, and can record the entire operation. The inclusion of the seminar or training to use BWC and ARD during the conduct of Basic Recruit Course will also prepare the police officers in their duties. With such, errors and mistakes in the use of BWC and ARD during actual police operations will be lessen. Also, the maintenance of a secured storage system for the recorded data is in line with the mandates of the Data Privacy Law. The Data Privacy Law protects the privacy of the individuals while ensuring free flow of information to promote innovation and growth, regulates the collection, recording, organization, storage, updating or modification, retrieval, consultation, use, consolidation, blocking, erasure or destruction of personal data, and ensures that the Philippines complies with international standards set for data protection through the National Privacy Commission.(Republic Act 10173, n.d.)

As to practicability of use, the officers emphasized that not all police operatives had their respective PNP-issued BWC or ARD. Hence, it shall not be obligatory considering that not all police stations have available devices. This sentiment of the officers is rooted from the fact that the BWC and ARD issued by the PNP are not sufficient for all police operatives. In an article written in 2021, the PNP commits to comply with the rules on BWC and ARD, although it acknowledged the fact that the organization does not have enough cameras for its personnel (Luna, 2021).

Police officers further pointed out that BWC and ARD shall only be used in overt police operations, and shall not be required in covert police activities, as it may compromise the operation, and worst, might put the life and safety of the officer conducting surveillance to imminent danger. It was also highlighted that the police operatives shall have advanced and continuous training on the use and maintenance of BWC and ARD in order to properly preserve its use and benefits.

In terms of effectiveness, the officers are of the view that in order for the use of BWC and ARD be effective in law enforcement activities, and to attain its objective, the devices to be procured shall be capable of recording comprehensive footage or video, the video as well as audio recording are clear, and the battery life of the device shall be long enough to cover the entire duration of the operation. This is consistent with the reality on the ground as displayed in one police operation in which the police officers reasoned out that the arrest that led to the death of a teenager was not recorded in BWC and ARD because said devices run out of batteries (*Chi, 2023*). In addition, police officers strongly suggest that the PNP shall raise awareness among citizens regarding the use and purpose of BWC and ARD in order to avoid instances in which the subject to be arrested refused to give his or her consent in recording the arrest.

With regard to the level of complexity of the documents required by the court, majority of police officers can comply with the required submissions of the court. Accordingly, this compliance is prompted by the fact that failure on their part shall give rise to liability of contempt of court. Hence, although it may be difficult and complicated, police officers find a way to comply with those so as to avoid any disciplinary action. Nevertheless, police officers advocate that extensive trainings and seminars shall be conducted to all police operatives for them to be familiar and competent in preparing court documents required related to the use of BWC and ARD.

Conclusions

After a thorough evaluation of the related literatures, existing laws and issuances, and the results of survey and interview among police officers, it can be concluded that police officers agree that the BWC and ARDs are necessary in various policing activities. The perceived benefits of these technologies in enhancing accountability, transparency, and legitimacy are well-supported by existing literature. However, mixed perceptions about the use of BWC and ARDs suggest areas where further training or policy adjustments may be needed to address practical concerns and ensure the effective implementation of BWCs in all aspects of policing.

It is further concluded that police officers generally find the use of BWCs and ARDs practical and beneficial in their operations. While there are some concerns about equipment availability, the overall perception is positive, indicating that with adequate

resources and continued training, the use of these technologies can significantly enhance police transparency and effectiveness.

The findings of the research further lead to the conclusion that there is a strong consensus among police officers on the effectiveness of BWCs and ARDs. The perceived benefits in terms of transparency, accountability, performance, prosecution support, and legal defense are well-supported by existing literature. These findings highlight the critical role that BWCs and ARDs play in modern policing, providing clear and objective evidence that enhances the overall effectiveness of law enforcement activities.

The findings of the research further concluded that policies officers feel well-prepared and capable of managing the documentation requirements associated with the use of BWCs and ARDs. The perceived reasonableness of these requirements and the officers' ability to comply effectively contribute to the successful integration of these technologies into policing practices, ultimately supporting transparency and accountability.

Recommendations

1. Procurement of high-quality BWC and ARD to be issued to all police operatives.
2. Inclusion of use of BWC and ARD in Basic Recruit Course (BRC).
3. Provision of system for storage and management of recorded data.
4. BWC and ARD shall be used only for overt operations, and shall be optional in covert operations.
5. Conduct of continuous training for the maintenance of BWC and ARD.
6. Conduct of extensive and continuous trainings for the preparation of court-required documents.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Research ethics is necessary for scientific integrity, human rights and dignity, and collaboration between science and society. This ensures that participation in studies is voluntary, informed and safe for research subjects. (Bhandari, 2021)

This study entitled, *Exploring Transparency: Police Officers' View on the Use of PNP Body-Worn Camera*, is the original work of the researchers and the latter further attest originality of this study and have cited all the references used.

Several ethical considerations were taken into account to ensure that this study was conducted in an appropriate manner. The participants had been informed of the purpose of the study and in turn, gave their verbal consent to the conduct of the survey and the roundtable discussion. The participants voluntarily participated in the survey and

they were assured that the information gathered will remain confidential and will be kept and be used for research purposes only.

The participants were further informed that they have the choice not to disclose their names in the survey form, and that they have been informed of their right to desist from participating as respondents in this study at any point. Permission from participants to take Minutes of the interview was likewise obtained.

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REFERENCES

- 1987 Constitution, Preamble.
- 1987 Constitution, Section 6, Article XVI.
- 1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 1, Article III.
- 1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 2, Article II.
- 1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 5, Article II.
- 1987 Philippine Constitution, Section 14, Article III.
- A.M. No. 21-06-08-SC. (n.d.). Retrieved April 30, 2024, from <https://sc.judiciary.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/21-06-08-SC2.pdf>
- Amnesty International. (2024). *What is Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Why it is Created?* <https://www.amnesty.org/en/about-us/contact/>
- Ariel, B., Farrar, W. A., & Sutherland, A. (2015). The Effect of Police Body-Worn Cameras on the Use of Force and Citizen's Complaints Against Police: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, 31(3), 509–535.
- Ariel, B., Sutherland, A., Henstock, D., Young, J., Drover, P., Sykes, J., & Henderson, R. (2016). Wearing body cameras increases assaults against officers and does not reduce police use of force: Results from a global multi-site experiment. *European Journal of Criminology*, 13(6), 744–755.
- Balagtas-See, A. (2021). Philippine Police Chief: No Law Requires Officers Wear Body Cameras. *Benar News*. <https://www.benarnews.org/english/news/philippine/body-cameras-06252021144413.html>
- Beller, J. (2021). *Recommendations and Best Practices for Body-Worn Camera Implementation: Use and Policy Implications for Law Enforcement Agencies and Suggested Guidelines for a Successful Program to Promote Community Transparency* [MA Thesis, University of Wisconsin]. <https://minds.wisconsin.edu/bitstream/handle/1793/82510/Beller%2C%20James.pdf?sequence=5&isAllowed=y>
- Benefits and Barriers to Implementing Police Body-Worn Cameras*. (n.d.). Better Canada Institute.
- Bhandari, P. (2021, October 18). *Ethical Considerations in Research*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/research-ethics/>

- Black's Law Dictionary*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://thelawdictionary.org/extrajudicial/>
- Braga, A. A., Sousa, W. H., Coldren, J. J. R., & Rodriguez, D. (2018). The Effects of Body-Worn Cameras on Police Activity and Police-Citizen Encounters: A Randomized Controlled Trial . *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 108(3), 511–538. <https://scholarlycommons.law.northwestern.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=7632&context=jclc>
- Braga, A., Coldren, J., Sousa, W., Rodriguez, D., & Alfer, O. (2017). The benefits of Body-Worn cameras: new findings from a randomized controlled trial at the Las Vegas Metropolitan Police Department. In *National Criminal Justice Reference Service, Office of the Justice Program*. <https://www.ojp.gov/pdffiles1/nij/grants/251416.pdf>
- Chi, C. (2023). Lawmakers bat for mandatory use of body cams after killing of Navotas teen. *PhilStar*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/08/15/2288834/lawmakers-bat-mandatory-use-body-cams-after-killing-navotas-teen>
- Conde, C. H. (2019, July 1). *Three-Year-Old Girl Latest Philippines 'Drug War' Victim*. Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2019/07/01/three-year-old-girl-latest-philippines-drug-war-victim>
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research* (3rd Edition). SAGE Publication Inc.,
- Crowder, S., & Turvey, B. E. (2013). *Ethical Justice: Applied Issues for Criminal Justice Students and Professionals*.
- Cubitt, T. I. C., Lesic, R., Myers, G. L., & Corry, R. (2017). Body-worn video: A systematic review of literature. *Australian & New Zealand Journal Criminology*, 50(3), 379–396.
- Gavilan, J. (2023, August 22). For witness to drug war deaths, ICC a chance for families to defend truth. *Rappler*. <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/witness-drug-war-deaths-international-criminal-court-chance-families-defend-truth/>
- Harris, D. A. (2010). Picture this: Body-worn video devices (“head cams”) as tools for ensuring fourth amendment compliance by police. *Texas Tech Law Review*, 43(1), 357–370.
- International Association of Chiefs of Police. (2019). Body-Worn Cameras. In *Law Enforcement Policy Center*. <https://www.theiacp.org/sites/default/files/2020-06/BWCs%20June%202020.pdf>
- Jennings, W. G., Lynch, M. D., & Fridell, L. A. (2015). Evaluating the impact of police body-worn cameras on arresting, prosecuting, and convicting criminal offenders. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 43(6), 504–508.
- Kroll, T., & Neri, M. (2009). *Designs for Mixed Methods Research* (S. Andrew & E. Halcomb, Eds.).
- Lee, J. (2021). Will body cameras help end police violence? *American Civil Liberties Union of Washington*. <https://www.aclu-wa.org/story/%C2%A0will-body-cameras-help-end-police-violence%C2%A0>
- Lum, C., Koper, C. S., & Merola, L. M. (2015). Existing and Ongoing Body Worn Camera Research: Knowledge Gaps and Opportunities. *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, 10(3), 292–302.
- Luna, F. (2021, August 3). PNP says “will find ways” to follow SC rules on body cameras despite lack of equipment. *PhilStar*.

- <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2021/08/03/2117286/pnp-says-will-find-ways-follow-sc-rules-body-cameras-despite-lack-equipment>
- McCarthy, J. (2021, September 15). *International Criminal Court Backs Probe Of Duterte's War On Drugs In The Philippines*. National Public Radio. <https://www.npr.org/2021/09/15/1037585416/philippines-duterte-drug-war-international-criminal-court-investigation>
- Macabingkil v. Yatco, et.al., G.R. No. L-23147 (1967).
- Pamaran, M. (2012). *Revised Rules of Criminal Procedure Annotated*. Central Book Supply Inc.,.
- Patton, M. Q. (1990). *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods*. SAGE Publication Inc.,.
- People v. Sapla, G.R. No. 204045 (2020).
- Philippines: End Police Torture, Killings*. (2015, January 29). Human Rights Watch. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2015/01/29/philippines-end-police-torture-killings>
- Philippines' "War on Drugs."* (n.d.). Human Rights Watch. Retrieved April 28, 2024, from <https://www.hrw.org/tag/philippines-war-drugs>
- PhilStar. (2019). Bill Seeking EJK Accountability Pushed. *PhilStar*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2019/07/07/1932764/bill-seeking-ejk-accountability-pushed>
- PNP Memorandum Circular 2018-009*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 30, 2024, from https://didm.pnp.gov.ph/images/james_vio/MC_No_2018-009_Operational_Guidelines_and_Policies_on_the_Use_of_Body_Worn_Camera.pdf
- PNP Police Operational Procedures, RULES 7 and 8*. (n.d.).
- Republic Act 6975, Section 24.
- Republic Act 10173.
- Restorative Justice, Probation and Parole Administration*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 28, 2024, from <https://probation.gov.ph/restorative-justice/>
- Revised Penal Code, Article 11, Paragraph 5.
- Revised Penal Code, Article 11 Paragraphs 1 to 3.
- Robinson, R. S. (2014). *Purposive Sampling* (A. C. Michalos, Ed.). Springer, Dordrecht.
- Sullivan, E. (2018, November 29). *3 Police Officers Found Guilty Of Murder In Philippines' War On Drugs*. National Public Radio. <https://www.npr.org/2018/11/29/671795507/3-police-officers-found-guilty-of-murder-in-philippines-war-on-drugs>
- Torres-Tupas, T. (2021). SC: Body Cameras now Mandatory When Serving Search, Arrest Warrant. *Inquirer.Net*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1458050/sc-body-cameras-when-serving-search-arrest-warrants-now-mandatory#ixzz8HpxbJCm3>
- United Nations Human Rights Special Rapporteur*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 29, 2024, from <https://www.ohchr.org/en/special-procedures/sr-executions>
- Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 10*. (n.d.). Retrieved April 28, 2024, from <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>
- Valle-Corpuz, M. (n.d.). *The Role and Function of the Prosecution in the Philippine Criminal Justice System*. Retrieved April 28, 2024, from https://www.unafei.or.jp/publications/pdf/RS_No53/No53_27PA_Corpuz.pdf
- Villareal III, E. M. (2017). *Political and Constitutional Law for Students, Barristers and Lawyers*. Rex Bookstore.

- White, M. D. (2014). *Police officer body-worn cameras: Assessing the evidence*. Washington, DC: Office of Justice Programs, US Department of Justice.
- Williams, M. Jr., Weil, N., Rasich, E., Ludwig, J., Chang, H., & Egrari, S. (2021). *Body-Worn Cameras in Policing: Benefits and Costs*. https://urbanlabs.uchicago.edu/attachments/fa10fa8358f9a374192f2360e0cf620dd4fcb523/store/5959e869f443a4b4feb02bb33edcc63e12308bcb279b0b3d08d673c23a27/Williams+et+al_Body-Worn+Cameras_03_25.pdf